

Learning vocabulary seems to be one of the easiest things about learning a language, but it's also one of the hardest things to do, especially when you have reached a certain level. Learning vocabulary needs practice and time and in our days time is a problem. We can face some difficulties, such as: deciding which words are worth learning. There are a lot of words in English compared with many other languages, and it is impossible to know them all – even native speakers frequently meet words they have never seen before in their reading

In conclusion, building a strong vocabulary is a gradual but deeply rewarding process. By reading regularly, listening to authentic materials, writing consistently, and practicing with tools like flashcards or vocabulary journals, learners can naturally strengthen their word knowledge. Learning synonyms, studying word roots, and grouping words by themes makes vocabulary richer and more flexible, helping avoid repetition and making speech more expressive.

**ARAB OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDA O‘ZBEKISTON
TASVIRI: “ASDAA OMAN” XABARLARI VA “DUNYO” AA TALQINI**

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada arab ommaviy axborot vositalarida O‘zbekiston tasvirining shakllanishi “Asdaa Oman” elektron gazetasi xabarlarini misolida tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, ushbu xabarlarining “Dunyo” axborot agentligi tomonidan o‘zbek tilida qayta talqin qilinishi, matnlar orasidagi leksik-semantik va uslubiy tafovutlar aniqlangan. Tadqiqot arabcha matnlarda diplomatik neytrallikning ustuvorligi, o‘zbekcha talqinlarda esa baholovchi birliklarning kuchayishi, mazmunning torayishi yoki kengayishi kabi jarayonlarni ko‘rsatadi. Natijalar O‘zbekistonning Yaqin Sharqdagi imijini shakllantirishda milliy axborot siyosati va tarjima jarayonining rolini yoritadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Oʻzbekiston imiji, arab OAV, Asdaa Oman, Dunyo AA, media diskurs, tarjima tahlili, semantik tafovut.

Abstract. This article analyzes the representation of Uzbekistan in Arab mass media through the example of news published by the electronic newspaper “Asdaa Oman.” It also examines how these reports are reinterpreted in Uzbek by the “Dunyo” Information Agency, identifying lexical-semantic and stylistic differences between the original texts and their translations. The study reveals that Arab media tend to maintain diplomatic neutrality, while Uzbek reinterpretations often intensify evaluative expressions, broaden or narrow meanings, and adapt the discourse for the local audience. The findings highlight the role of national media policy and translation practices in shaping Uzbekistan’s image in the Middle East.

Keywords: Uzbekistan’s image, Arab media, Asdaa Oman, Dunyo Agency, media discourse, translation analysis, semantic variation.

المخلص: تتناول هذه المقالة صورة أوزبكستان في وسائل الإعلام العربية من خلال تحليل الأخبار المنشورة في صحيفة «أصداء عُمان» الإلكترونية، ومقارنتها بالطريقة التي تعيد بها وكالة «دُنْيُو» الأوزبكية تقديم هذه الأخبار باللغة الأوزبكية. ويكشف التحليل عن فروق لغوية ودلالية وأسلوبية بين النصوص الأصلية والترجمات، حيث تحافظ الكتابة العربية على درجة عالية من الحياد الدبلوماسي، بينما تميل النسخ الأوزبكية إلى تعزيز الطابع التقييمي وتوسيع أو تضيق المعنى بما يخدم المتلقي المحلي. وتبرز النتائج دور السياسة الإعلامية الوطنية والترجمة في تشكيل صورة أوزبكستان في الفضاء العربي.

الكلمات المفتاحية: صورة أوزبكستان، الإعلام العربي، أصداء عُمان، وكالة دُنْيُو، الخطاب الإعلامي، تحليل الترجمة، الفروق الدلالية.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается формирование образа Узбекистана в арабских средствах массовой информации на примере материалов электронного издания «Asdaa Oman». Также анализируется, как эти сообщения интерпретируются на узбекском языке информационным агентством «Dunyo». Выявлены лексико-семантические и стилистические различия между оригинальными текстами и их переводами. Исследование показывает, что арабские материалы отличаются дипломатической нейтральностью, тогда как узбекские интерпретации усиливают оценочные элементы и адаптируют содержание к местной аудитории. Полученные результаты раскрывают роль национальной медиаполитики и переводческих процессов в формировании имиджа Узбекистана на Ближнем Востоке.

Ключевые слова: имидж Узбекистана, арабские СМИ, Asdaa Oman, агентство Dunyo, медиадискурс, анализ перевода, семантические различия.

Arab davlatlarida O‘zbekiston haqidagi tasavvurlar ko‘p hollarda siyosiy aloqalar, iqtisodiy hamkorlik va madaniy muloqotlarga tayanib shakllanadi. Ammo bu tasavvurlarni keng ommaga yetkazuvchi asosiy vosita baribir ommaviy axborot vositalaridir. Arab davlatlari matbuoti, xususan O‘man Sultonligida faoliyat yuritayotgan nashrlar, jumlada “Asdaa Oman” elektron nashri O‘zbekistonning mintaqaviy maydondagi o‘rni, uning tashqi siyosati, iqtisodiy islohotlari va investitsion salohiyatini kengroq auditoriyaga taqdim etib kelmoqda.

Nashr O‘zbekiston haqida siyosiy uchrashuvlardan tortib savdo-iqtisodiy loyihalargacha, regional transport yo‘laklaridan turizm sohasidagi islohotlarga bo‘lgan mavzularni muntazam yoritib kelmoqda. Gazetaning tili diplomatik, mulohazalari ehtiyotkor, mavzularni tanlashda mantiqiy izchillik bor. Bu materiallar Ko‘rfaz auditoriyasining O‘zbekistonni qanday ko‘rayotgani, uni qanday davlat sifatida qabul qilayotgani haqida ishonchli tasavvur beradi. Arab matbuotidagi terminlar, baholovchi birliklar, sintaktik qurilmalar mamlakatning qanday qiyofada gavdalanishini belgilovchi kuchli nutqiy vositalardir.

Shu bilan birga, arab matbuotida paydo bo‘lgan ushbu tasvirlar o‘zbek o‘quvchisiga yetib borguncha yana bir bosqichdan o‘tadi: tarjima va qayta talqin. “Dunyo” axborot agentligi “Asdaa Oman” maqolalarini muntazam ravishda o‘zbek tiliga ko‘chirib, mahalliy auditoriyaga taqdim etadi.

“Asdaa Oman” elektron gazetasi O‘zbekiston haqidagi xabarlarni yoritishda diplomatik muvozanatni saqlagan holda, har bir mavzuni faktlar asosida beradi. Shu bilan birga, matndagi iboralarning tanlovi mamlakatni qanday ko‘rinishda tasvirlashni belgilab qo‘yadi. Xabarlar o‘zbek tiliga ko‘chirilganida esa bu tasvirning ayrim qatlamlari kuchayadi, ayrimlari esa soddalashtiriladi. Shuning uchun arabcha matn va o‘zbekcha tarjima o‘rtasidagi farqlarni leksik-semantik, uslubiy hamda diskursiv jihatdan kuzatish juda qiziqarli.

Iqtisodiy prognozga bag‘ishlangan maqolada “Asdaa Oman” O‘zbekiston iqtisodiyotining 7,5 foiz o‘shishi kutilayotganini sodda va hech qanday ortiqcha baholashsiz bayon qiladi. Arabcha matndagi “من المتوقع” birikmasi ehtiyotkor optimizmni bildiradi; u hali yuz bermagan, ammo asosga ega jarayonni ifodalaydi. O‘zbek tilidagi variantda xabar mazmuni to‘g‘ri berilgan bo‘lsa-da, arab matnida mavjud bo‘lgan vaqt aniqligi yo‘qoladi¹. Bu farq xabarning semantik tuzilishiga bevosita ta’sir ko‘rsatadi: arabcha matn fakt atrofida turadi, o‘zbekcha esa faktni umumlashtirib beradi.

¹“Asdaa Oman” gazetasi: O‘zbekiston iqtisodiyoti 7,5 foizga oshishi kutilmoqda // dunyo.uz. – 2025. – 12-dekabr. – URL: <https://dunyo.info/uz/news/asdaa-oman-gazetasi-ozbekiston-iqtisodiyoti-75-foizga-oshishi-kutilmoqda> (arab tilida: <https://asdaaoman.com/?p=118609>) (murojaat sanasi: 13.12.2025).

Sun'iy intellekt bo'yicha xabarda arab nashri "توسيع استخدام تقنيات الذكاء الاصطناعي في المؤسسات الأوزبكية" iborasidan foydalanadi. Bu iboraning har bir unsuri aniq: texnologiyalar, idoralar, qo'llanish jarayoni. Demak, matn ma'lumot berish vazifasini to'liq bajaradi, jarayonning qamrovi ko'rsatilgan. O'zbekcha tarjimada esa mazmuni tashkil etuvchi ikki muhim unsur — texnologiyalar va idoralar — tushirib qoldiriladi. Natijada, jarayon tasvirining chegarasi keng emas, balki umumiy ko'lamda ko'rinadi. Bunday o'zgarish xabarni soddalashtiradi, lekin informativ aniqlikni kamaytiradi².

Qatar bilan hamkorlik haqidagi materiallar esa bu ikki diskurs o'rtasidagi farqning yanada nozik shaklini ko'rsatadi. Arabcha "أحد الشركاء الموثوقين" iborasi diplomatik mulohaza bilan tanlangan bo'lib, bu so'zning o'zi matbuotda ham ko'p qo'llanadi va odatda bir davlatning boshqasiga nisbatan ishonch darajasini bildiradi. O'zbekcha variant mazmun jihatdan to'liq mos keladi; uning uslubida ortiqcha emotsional bo'yoq yo'q, matn diplomatik ohangni saqlagan. Shunga qaramay, sintaktik tuzilma o'zbek o'quvchisiga mos shaklga tushirilgani sababli ohangdagi yumshoq kuchayish seziladi³.

Saudiya Arabistoni bilan hamkorlik yoritilgan xabarda muallif "التعاون المثمر" iborasini tanlaydi. Bu ibora diplomatik matnlarda samarali hamkorlikni nazarda tutadi, lekin keskin, baholovchi ohangga ega emas. O'zbekcha "sermahsul hamkorlik" mazmunga mos keladi va semantik ekvivalentni taqdim etadi⁴.

Turizm sohasi yoritilgan xabar esa semantik kengaytirishning eng yaqqol ko'rinishidir. Arabcha matn O'zbekistonning turistik mavqeining mustahkamlanayotganini bildiradi: «تعزير مكانة أوزبكستان السياحية». O'zbekcha talqinda esa bu ibora "jahon turizmining yetakchi kuchiga aylanish" tarzida kengaytiriladi⁵. Mana shu joyda tarjima material mazmunini kengaytirib, xabarni milliy imijni mustahkamlash tomoniga yo'naltirgani ko'rinadi. Bu jarayon ilmiy adabiyotlarda

² "Asdaa Oman" gazetasi: O'zbekistonda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish ko'lami kengaymoqda // dunyo.uz. – 2025. – 6-dekabr. – URL: <https://dunyo.info/news/gazeta-asdaa-oman-uzbekistan-rasshiraet-primenenie-iskusstvennogo> (arab tilida: <https://asdaaoman.com/?p=117599>) (murojaat sanasi: 13.12.2025).

³ "Asdaa Oman": So'nggi yillarda Qatar amirligi O'zbekistonning Yaqin Sharqdagi ishonchli hamkorlaridan biriga aylanmoqda // dunyo.uz. – 2025. – 5-noyabr. – URL: <https://dunyo.info/uz/mir-ob-uzbekistane/%E2%80%9CAsdaa-Oman%E2%80%9D-s%D1%9Enggi-yillarda-%D2%9Aatar-amirligi-%D0%8Ezbekistonning-ya%D2%9Bin-shar%D2%9Bdagi-ishonchli-%D2%B3amkorlaridan-biriga-aylanmo%D2%9Bda> (arab tilida: <https://asdaaoman.com/?p=113545>) (murojaat sanasi: 13.12.2025).

⁴ "Asdaa Oman": O'zbekiston-Saudiya ko'p qirrali sheriklik munosabatlari yuksak darajaga ko'tarildi // dunyo.uz. – 2025. – 17-oktyabr. – URL: https://dunyo.info/uz/about_uzb/plodotvornoe-sotrudnichestvo-uzbekistana-i-saudovskoy-aravii-v-fokuse-Asdaa-Oman (arab tilida: <https://asdaaoman.com/?p=111376>) (murojaat sanasi: 13.12.2025).

⁵ "Asdaa Oman" gazetasi: O'zbekistonning "BMT-Turizm" tashkiloti bilan hamkorligi mamlakatning jahon turizmining yetakchi kuchiga aylanishida muhim rol o'ynadi // dunyo.uz. – 2025. 21-sentyabr. – URL: <https://dunyo.info/uz/mir-ob-uzbekistane/%E2%80%9CAsdaa-Oman%E2%80%9D-gazetasi-%D0%8Ezbekistonning-%E2%80%9Cbmt-turizm%E2%80%9D-tashkiloti-bilan-%D2%B3amkorligi-mamlakatning-zha%D2%B3on-turizmining-etakchi-kuchiga-aylanishida-mu%D2%B3im-rol-%D1%9Eynadi> (arab tilida: <https://asdaaoman.com/?p=107628>) (murojaat sanasi: 13.12.2025).

“diskursiv rekonstruksiya” sifatida baholanadi: mazmun o‘zgarmaydi, ammo uning taqdimoti kuchayadi.

Madaniy-tarixiy tasvir berilgan maqolada esa aksincha: arabcha matnning poetik tasviri o‘zbekcha talqinda kuchaytirilgan. “موسيقى حية” iborasida badiiylilik bor, lekin u ehtiyotkor. O‘zbekcha “jonli musiqasi” esa yanada obrazli, yanada jozibali. Bu o‘zgarish matnning badiiy og‘irligini orttiradi⁶.

Bu kuzatishlarning barchasi shuni ko‘rsatadiki, arabcha matnda neytral iboralar ko‘p, baholovchi birliklar kam. O‘zbekcha matnda esa baholash kuchayishi, semantik kengayish yoki torayish, poetik intensivlik kabi hodisalar ko‘proq uchraydi.

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